

Cadmium (II) Complexes with Substituted Pyridines

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Four non-electrolytic, tetra-coordinated cadmium complexes having the formula $[CdL_2X_2]$ where L is 4-vinyl pyridine and X is Cl^- , Br, I or CNS^- are reported. Also, three compounds having the formula $CdLX_2$ where L is 4-methyl pyridine or 2-amino 4-methyl pyridine and X is Cl^- or Br^- have been obtained. These apparently three-coordinated compounds are also presumably tetra-coordinated through halogen bridging. I.R. spectra of all the complexes are recorded.

Divalent Cadmium ion has a completely filled d^0 electronic structure and forms stable four-coordinated tetrahedral complexes involving the use of sp^3 hybrid orbitals. Many such compounds have been reported¹ in the literature. Several complexes have been isolated²⁻⁵ with ligands containing nitrogen donor atoms. In this communication, we report some more complexes obtained by reacting cadmium halides with substituted pyridines, viz., 4-vinyl pyridine, 4-methyl pyridine (γ -picoline) and 2-amino 4-methyl pyridine.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used are of A.R. grade. The compounds were prepared in ethanolic medium by reacting stoichiometric quantities of cadmium halide and the ligands. There was an almost immediate formation of the compound. All the compounds were suction filtered, washed with absolute alcohol, then with light petroleum and finally dried *in vacuo*.

The purity of the isolated compounds was established by estimating the metal and the halogen. The metal was precipitated and weighed as $CdNH_4PO_4 \cdot H_2O$. The halogen was estimated as silver halide after digesting the compounds with dilute nitric acid to avoid the interference of the ligands. The conductance measurements were carried out using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge type CLO102 and a dip type cell. The relevant analytical and conductance data are recorded in Table I.

The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made over solid specimens at room temperature using Gouy method and all the compounds were found to be diamagnetic. The infra-red absorption spectra of these complexes as nujol mulls were recorded in the region 5000—650 cm^{-1} using a Unicam SP200 double beam spectrophotometer with rock salt optics. The absorption bands of the free ligands and the complexes are recorded in Table II.

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TABLE I

Analysis, M. P. and conductance of Cadmium (II) complexes with substituted Pyridines.

Name of the complex	Formula	M.P. °C	% Cadmium		% Halogen		Λ_m (mhos) in acetone
			Calcd	Found	Calcd	Found	
Dichloro bis-4-Vinyl pyridine Cadmium (II)	[Cd (4V.P.) ₂ Cl ₂]	> 260	28.6	30.8	18.1	18.8	insoluble
Dibromo bis-4-Vinyl pyridine Cadmium (II)	[Cd (4V.P.) ₂ Br ₂]	> 260	23.3	22.3	33.2	31.6	37.4
Diiodo bis-4-Vinyl pyridine Cadmium (II)	[Cd (4V.P.) ₂ I ₂]	126	19.5	18.3	44.2	43.5	10.0
Dithiocyanato bis-4Vinyl pyridine Cadmium (II)	[Cd (4V.P.) ₂ (CN S) ₂]	200	25.6	24.7	26.6	26.8	insoluble
Dichloro γ -picoline Cadmium (II)	[Cd (γ -pico) Cl ₂]	> 260	40.6	39.8	25.6	25.1	insoluble
Dibromo γ -picoline Cadmium (II)	[Cd (γ -pico) Br ₂]	> 260	30.7	31.7	43.7	41.1	insoluble
Dichloro 2-amino 4-methyl pyridine Cadmium (II)	[Cd (2Am. 4Me. Py) ₂ Cl ₂]	> 260	38.6	33.4	34.3	24.3	insoluble

TABLE II

Infrared absorption bands (cm⁻¹) in Nujol mulls of Cadmium(II) complexes with substituted Pyridines.

L	L=4-vinyl pyridine			CdL ₂ (CNS) ₂ L	L= γ -picoline		L=2 amino γ -picoline		
	CdL ₂ Cl ₂	CdL ₂ Br ₂	CdL ₂ I ₂		CdLCl ₂	CdLBr ₂	L	CdLCl ₂	
808(s)	—	—	818(s)	820(s)	742(s)	745(br)	742(br)	740(s)	740(vw)
852(vs)	860(s)	860	855(vs)	858 (vs)	823(s)	830(s)	822(s)	810(vs)	812(vs)
950(s)	950(s)	950(vs)	950(vs)	960(vs)	1015(vs)	1040(s)	1038(w)	880(vs)	866(s)
1010(vs)	1010(w)	1010(s)	1005(s)	1002(vs)	—	—	—	960(w)	—
	1030(w)	1030(s)	1025(s)	1030(vs)	1060(m)	1092(w)	1085(w)	980(w)	—
								1002(vs)	1015(w)
1081(w)	—	1090(vw)	1085(s)	1085(w)	1235(s)	—	1240(w)	1055(w)	—
1230(m)	1240(m)	1240(w)	1232(s)	1240(s)	1430(w)	—	—	1186(s)	—
								1280(vs)	—
1245(m)	—	—	1250(sh)	—	1460(w)	1470(sh)	—	1320(vs)	1325(s)
1422(vs)	1425(w)	1430(w)	1422(w)	1425(vw)	—	—	—	—	—
								1440(w)	1460(sh)
								1470(sh)	1610(vs)
1508(s)	1510(sh)	1520(w)	1510(sh)	—	1622(s)	1620(s)	1620(s)	1560(vs)	1570(s)
1558(s)	1558(w)	1560(w)	1558(w)	1560(vw)	—	—	—	1615(s)	1618(s)
1600(vs)	1615(vs)	1620(vs)	1615(vs)	1620(vs)	—	—	—	1642(s)	1638(s)
								1900(w)	—
								3400(s)	3420(w)
				2170(vs)					

s-sharp, vs-very sharp, w-weak, m-medium, sh-shoulder, br-broad.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The relative affinities of ligand atoms for different acceptor molecules and ions have been summarised by Chatt *et al*⁶. Accordingly, Zinc belongs to class (a) acceptors which form most stable complexes with the first ligand atom of each group, i.e., with nitrogen, oxygen

and fluorine and mercury belongs to class (b) acceptors which form stable complexes with the second or subsequent ligand atom of the group. Cadmium ion exhibits both class (a) and class (b) characters. We had reported earlier stable sulphur-bonded complexes of mercury(II)⁷ and nitrogen-bonded complexes of Zinc (II)⁸. Divalent cadmium is expected to form stable complexes with nitrogen as well as sulphur ligands. Since it has a $4d^{10}$ configuration, it usually forms perfect tetrahedral complexes utilising $5s5p^3$ hybrid orbitals for bonding, leaving a perfectly symmetrical $d^4y d^6z$ non-bonding shell which causes least perturbation to the preferred stereochemical shape.

The dihalo bis- (4-vinyl pyridine) Cadmium(II) complexes are non-electrolytes in acetone medium. They are tetra-coordinated and are presumably tetrahedral. The iodo and thiocyanato compounds, melt at low temperatures like any other covalently bonded, monomeric complex. But the corresponding chloro and bromo compounds do not melt or decompose upto 260° . This may be indicative of polymerisation through halogen bridges which increases the coordination number. This may be probable since the chloride and bromide are weakly polarisable ligands compared to iodide and hence the charge transfer per each σ -bond will be smaller here than in the case of iodide. The molecular complexity could not be established due to poor solubility of the compounds.

The compounds having the formula $(dLX)_2$ where L is 4-methyl pyridine and 2-amino 4-methyl pyridine and X is Cl^- or Br^- are only apparently three-coordinated. They have very high melting points beyond 260° and are insoluble in all common organic solvents. Hence they are definitely not monomers and can be represented by the following structure :

FIG. 1

They have tetrahedral structures but, for the sake of convenience, planar configurations have been shown.

The infra-red absorption bands of these complexes recorded in Table II follow the general pattern of coordination complexes. As expected, most of the ligand absorption bands are either split or shifted to a shorter wavelength or a higher frequency region. Direct metal-ligand stretching frequencies could not be recorded since they are beyond the range of the spectrophotometer used. In this connection, it may be mentioned that Frank and Rogers⁹, while studying the metal-pyridine, substituted pyridine and quinoline complexes in the range $667-150\text{ cm}^{-1}$, could obtain direct evidence of metal-ligand bonding.

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The characteristic thiocyanate absorption ($2100-2200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) is noticed at 2170 cm^{-1} . Chatt and Duncanson¹⁰ suggested the regions of absorption for terminal and bridging thiocyanate groups but at this stage, it is not possible to say definitely whether the thiocyanate is present as a terminal or a bridging group in the present case.

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